

Syntheses of N-Mannich Bases of Benzamide and Their Preliminary Pharmacological Testing

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Some N-Mannich bases of benzamide have been prepared using heterocyclic secondary amines. These bases and their salts have been estimated in non-aqueous media. On preliminary pharmacological testing they were found to possess some C.N.S. depressant activity as well as a cardiac stimulant activity.

DANDIYA and coworkers¹ have reported that the compound 'N'-(4-diethylaminophenyl)-3,4,5-trimethoxybenzamide resembles C.N.S. stimulants like amphetamine, cocaine and caffeine. For the introduction of smaller basic alkyl chains, a very expedient and elegant method is available in Mannich condensation² and hence a few N-Mannich bases of benzamide were synthesized with a view to test them for C.N.S. stimulant activity.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected and recorded in an open capillary.

The N-Mannich bases of benzamide NSS_1 and NSS_2 , using morpholine and piperidine hydrochlorides respectively have been prepared by a procedure, described in literature³.

The Mannich base NSS_3 using piperazine was prepared by a procedure as follows :

Piperazine (2.42 g ; 0.0125 m) was added to benzamide (3 g ; 0.025 m) in methanol (10 ml). Formaldehyde (38% soln. 2 ml ; 0.025 m) was added drop by drop with cooling and stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr on a water bath. After the removal of about two-third of the solvent by distillation, the reaction mixture was chilled. The precipitated Mannich base was filtered, washed with Methanol and dried. It was crystallized from methanol-acetone as colourless crystals, m.p. 210-12, yield 2.5 g. (ca. 58%).

Thus NSS_1 and NSS_2 are the Mannich bases in the hydrochloride salt form (crystallized from ethanol-acetone) while NSS_3 is the Mannich base in the free base form.

Syntheses of Mannich bases of benzamide with pyrrolidine, dimethylamine and diethylamine were also attempted but no conclusive results were obtained.

Estimation of Mannich bases and their hydrochlorides in non-aqueous media :

The N-Mannich bases of benzamide behave as Lewis bases, accepting a proton on the nitrogen atom of the aminoalkyl moiety and accordingly have been estimated⁴ by visual titration with acetous perchloric acid using acetous crystal violet solution B.P. as indicator. The hydrochlorides of the Mannich bases have been estimated by the same procedure, after the addition of mercuric acetate⁵ to the solution of the salt. Mercuric acetate replaces the halide ion of the salt by an equivalent quantity of acetate ion, which is a strong base is acetic acid.

These estimations serve as a method for the determination of equivalent weight of a N-Mannich base and its hydrochloride salt (Table 1).

Preliminary Pharmacological Testing :

(1) Effect on locomotor activity :

The procedure followed was as employed by Menon and Dandiya⁶. All the compounds were administered by intraperitoneal route in a dose of 5 mg/kg body weight of rats and control animals received 0.4 mg/100 g of distilled water. Compounds NSS_1 and NSS_2 were administered in the form of solution in distilled water (1%) while the compound NSS_3 as emulsion in Tween 80 (1%) and the respective control animals received Tween 80 (1%) in distilled water.

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TABLE 1—N-MANNICH BASES OF BENZAMIDE
PhCONH—R

Sl. No.	-R	m. p. °C	Yield. %	Molecular Formula	Elemental analysis Found			Elemental analysis Required			Equivalent wt	
					C	H	N	C	H	N	Found	Required
NSS ₁	Morpholinomethyl	180-82 (ethanol-acetone)	72	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ .HCl	56.41	6.65	11.01	56.25	6.25	10.98	254	256.5
NSS ₂	Piperidinomethyl	186-88 (ethanol-acetone)	55	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O.HCl	61.55	7.97	10.82	61.41	7.04	11.02	252.3	254.5
NSS ₃	(N-benzamido-methyl) piperazinomethyl	210-12 (methanol-acetone)	58	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂	68.20	6.81	15.92	68.81	6.81	15.97	350.6	359

The results are tabulated below :

Compound	Locomotor activity
Control	++ +
NSS ₁	+
NSS ₂	+
NSS ₃	+

(2) Effect on ethanol induced hypnosis :

The method employed was that of Dandiya and Cullumbine⁷. Rats of either sex weighing between 100-120 g were divided into groups of five animals each. The test compounds were injected intraperitoneally in a dose of 5 mg/kg. After 15 minutes of the test compound administration, ethanol was injected in a dose of 3.0 g/kg intraperitoneally. Control groups of rats received distilled water, or Tween 80 (1%) in distilled water.

The results were tabulated below :

Compound	Dose of test compound	Dose of ethanol	Time of sleeping (Mean)
NSS ₁	5 mg/kg	3.00 g/kg	50 min.
NSS ₂	5 mg/kg	3.00 g/kg	70 min.
NSS ₃	5 mg/kg	3.00 g/kg	(two rats died)
NSS ₃	5 mg/kg	3.00 g/kg	55 min.
Water control	"	3.00 g/kg	30 min.
Emulsion of water with Tween 80(1%) control	"	3.00 g/kg	35 min.

(3) Effect on frog's heart :

The experiments were carried out according to the method of Bulbring (quoted by Burn)⁸. The ventricular contractions were recorded on a slowly moving smoked drum through Sterling's heart lever. Different doses of the compounds ranging from 0.75 mg to 1.5 mg were injected in a fixed volume (0.1 ml) of frog's heart perfusion ringer solution and effects on heart rate and amplitude were observed.

The observations were tabulated as below :

Compound	No. of heart beats/min after administration of compounds in different doses			
	Normal	0.75 mg	1 mg	1.5 mg
NSS ₁	40	42	44	64
NSS ₂	40	40	46	54
NSS ₃	40	40	42	46

Conclusion

The preliminary pharmacological testing of Mannich bases, under study, exhibited a decrease in locomotor activity, increase in ethanol induced hypnosis and increase in heart rate. These findings are suggestive that these compounds are C.N.S. depressants and possess cardiac stimulant property.

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